

A NEW DISTRIBUTION — L PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION FUNCTION

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Abstract: During study of problem for geostrophic and static equilibrium in atmosphere L distribution function was deduced. L function possesses unique parameter θ_M , Comparing with other famous probability distribution L distribution function has similarly certain properties such as , (1) variance is $(\theta_M/3)^2$; standard variance is $\theta_M/3$, mathematical expectation equal to zero, (2) fourth moment $(\theta_M)^4/125$, coefficient of kurtosis is 0.24, which more 0.24 than that of Normal distribution function. Third moment and coefficient of skew are both zero. (3) m -th moment exist, probability is equal to $2/e$ (74.04%) within coverage of $(-\theta_M/e < \theta < \theta_M/e)$; probability approximately 70.04% within coverage of $(-\theta_M/3 < \theta < \theta_M/3)$; (5) Continuous random variables of L function thickly more scatter in area near to its mean value than Normal distribution function does.

Key words: L probability density function; variance; expected value; the coefficient of kurtosis; m -th moment

1, probability function

1.1 probability density function

Assumed some physical system to be falling into L distribution in damped physical system, L probability density function may be postulated as below;

$$f(\theta) = \frac{1}{4\theta_M} \ln\left(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta}\right)^2 \quad (-\theta_M < \theta < \theta_M) \quad (1)$$

Here, θ is the random variable, θ_M is initial value and maximum amplitude when $t=0$ and also unique parameter in the function. as θ is approaching 0 ,L function has the odd singularity point, however, any its integral function tends to convergence, shown as Fig 1.

1.2 m -th moment of L function

When m is denoted even

$$v_m = \frac{1}{4\theta_M} \int_{-\theta_M}^{\theta_M} \theta^m \ln\left(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta}\right)^2 d\theta = \frac{\theta_M^m}{(m+1)^2}$$

$m=2$ (variance) , $m=4$ (fourth moment)

When m is denoted odd

$$v_m = \frac{1}{4\theta_M} \int_{-\theta_M}^{\theta_M} \theta^m \ln\left(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta}\right)^2 d\theta = 0$$

$m=1$ (expected value) , $m=3$ (third moment, respectively .

In proof of above, below can be certified firstly by using L'Hopital's Rule

$$\lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \frac{2}{m+1} \theta^{m+1} \ln \theta \rightarrow \frac{2}{(m+1)} \frac{\lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \ln \theta}{\lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\theta^{m+1}}} \rightarrow 0$$

1.3 The distribution function

We integrate formula (1), L probability density function, and then distribution function is verified below

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$$F(\theta) = \frac{1}{4\theta_M} \{ [\theta \ln(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta})^2 + 2\theta] + 2\theta_M \}$$

$$(-\theta_M < \theta < \theta_M)$$

Certainly $F'(\theta) = f(\theta)$

1.4 The how many of probability in any interval (θ_1, θ_2)

According to the theorem

$$P(a < Y < b) = F(b) - F(a), -\infty < a \leq b < \infty$$

Therefore the probability of any interval (θ_1, θ_2)

for L distribution is calculated via below formula

$$P(\theta_1 < \theta < \theta_2) = F(\theta_2) - F(\theta_1)$$

$$= \frac{1}{4\theta_M} \int_{\theta_1}^{\theta_2} \ln(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta})^2 d\theta$$

$$= \frac{1}{4\theta_M} \{ [\theta_2 \ln(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta_2})^2 + 2\theta_2] - [\theta_1 \ln(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta_1})^2 + 2\theta_1] \}$$

$$(-\theta_M < \theta < \theta_M)$$

For example

Fig.1 L probability density function

$P(\theta_1 < \theta < \theta_2) = 2/e$ (approximately 74.04%),

If $\theta_1 = -\theta_M/e$, $\theta_2 = \theta_M/e$,

Here $e = 2.718281828459$, obviously θ_M/e is very closer to $(\theta_M/3)$, comparatively, the probability, the Normal distribution lies in the interval

between $\pm\sigma$ (its standard deviation), is 68.3% or

so, but the probability of L distribution is nearly

exact 70.0% in same interval. In addition,

the limit of formula above exists when

$\theta_1 \rightarrow 0, \theta_2 \rightarrow 0$, shown as Fig 1 and Fig 2.

1.6 The exist of distribution function when closer to zero

$$\lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} F(\theta) = \lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \ln(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta})^{\frac{\theta}{2\theta_M}} + \frac{\theta}{2\theta_M} \Big|_{\theta \rightarrow 0} + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$= \lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \ln(\theta_M)^{\frac{\theta}{2\theta_M}} - \lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \ln(\theta)^{\frac{\theta}{2\theta_M}} + \frac{\theta}{2\theta_M} \Big|_{\theta \rightarrow 0} + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$= \frac{1}{2}$$

Fig.2 L probability distribution function

Above similarly through L'Hopital's Rule

$$\lim_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \ln(\theta) \frac{\theta}{2\theta_M} = 0$$

1.5 Demonstration of density function and distribution function

In fig 1 there

$$P(-\theta_M/e < \theta < \theta_M/e) \approx 74\%$$

$$P(\theta_M/e < \theta < \theta_M) \approx 13\%$$

$$P(-\theta_M < \theta < \theta_M/e) \approx 13\%$$

$(\theta_M - \theta_M/e) / \theta_M \approx 62.9\% \approx 61.8\%$ (golden section)

$$f(\theta) \rightarrow \infty, (\theta=0), f(\theta) \rightarrow 0, (\theta = \pm\theta_M)$$

In fig 2 also

$$AB = DE = (1/2) - (1/e) = 13\%$$

$$BC = CD = (1/e) = 37\%$$

$$BD = BC + CD = (2/e) = 74\%$$

$$AE = AB + BC + CD + DE = 1 - (2/e) + (2/e) = 100\%$$

2, L distribution characteristics

2.1 Some important characteristics

Expected value

$$M(\theta) = \frac{1}{4\theta_M} \int_{-\theta_M}^{\theta_M} \theta \ln\left(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta}\right)^2 d\theta = 0 \quad (-\theta_M < \theta < \theta_M)$$

Variance

$$v_2 = D(\theta) = \frac{1}{4\theta_M} \int_{-\theta_M}^{\theta_M} \theta^2 \ln\left(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta}\right)^2 d\theta = \left(\frac{\theta_M}{3}\right)^2$$

Standard deviation

$$\sigma = \frac{\theta_M}{3}$$

Third moment

$$v_3 = \frac{1}{4\theta_M} \int_{-\theta_M}^{\theta_M} \theta^3 \ln\left(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta}\right)^2 d\theta = 0$$

Coefficient of skew

$$\frac{v_3}{\sigma^3} = 0$$

Fourth moment

$$v_4 = \frac{1}{4\theta_M} \int_{-\theta_M}^{\theta_M} \theta^4 \ln\left(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta}\right)^2 d\theta = \frac{\theta_M^4}{25}$$

Coefficient of kurtosis

$$\frac{v_4}{\sigma^4} - 3 = 0.24$$

2.2 Comparison between L distribution and Normal distribution

Probability of L distribution and normal distribution when θ in the context of σ ; 2σ ; 3σ , respectively, here σ denote respective standard deviation

L distribution

$$P(-\sigma < \theta < \sigma) = 0.70$$

$$P(-2\sigma < \theta < 2\sigma) = 0.94$$

$$P(-3\sigma < \theta < 3\sigma) = 1$$

Normal distribution [1~2]

$$P(-\sigma < x < \sigma) = 0.683$$

$$P(-2\sigma < \theta < 2\sigma) = 0.955$$

$$P(-3\sigma < \theta < 3\sigma) = 0.997$$

2.2 Comparison between L distribution and some other well-known distribution

Tab1 difference of some basic parameter for some distribution

The classification of distribution function	Mean	variance	4th central moment	CFK*
(Normal)	μ	σ^2	3.0	0
(Exponential)	$1/\lambda$	$1/\lambda^2$	9.0	6
(Gamma)	a/λ^2	a/λ^2	$3+6a$	b/a
“(Uniform)	$(a+b)/2$	$(a-b)^2/12$	1.8	-1.2
(Logarithm)	0	$(\theta_M/3)^2$	3.24	0.24

*CFK is abbreviated of Coefficient of Kurtosis.

The curve of distribution becomes shape of sunken or hollow and depressed as $CFK < -1.2$.

2.3 Determination numerical value of $\theta = \theta_a(2/e) = \theta_a(74.04\%)$ and Where is θ as probability $= 2/e$

Define follow

$$\int_{-\theta_M}^{\theta_a} f(\theta) d\theta = \frac{2}{e} + \frac{e-2}{2e} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{e}$$

$$\int_{-\theta_M}^{-\theta_a} f(\theta) d\theta = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{e}$$

Also

$$\frac{1}{4\theta_M} \{ [-\theta_a \ln(\frac{\theta_M}{\theta_a})^2 - 2\theta_a] + 2\theta_M \} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{e}$$

$$\frac{1}{4\theta_M} \{ [\theta_a \ln(\frac{-\theta_M}{\theta_a})^2 + 2\theta_a] + 2\theta_M \} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{e}$$

Determine θ_a , finally by solution, $\theta_a (2/e) = \pm \theta_M/e$.

coefficient of skew is zero, imply L symmetric around zero, the coefficient of kurtosis 0.24, standard deviation $\theta_M/3$, variance $(\theta_M/3)^2$.

3, summaries

in a word ,L distribution with only one parameter θ_M is shown as its mean 0 ,its variance $(\theta_M/3)^2$, its standard deviation $\theta_M/3$, its fourth moment $(\theta_M)^4/25$, third moment zero, the coefficient of kurtosis 0.24, coefficient of skew is zero ,m-th moment $(\theta_M)^m/(m+1)^2$, in addition, other

characteristic

,ratio of $(\theta_M - \theta_M/e) / \theta_M$ nearly to golden ratio, as well as $P(-\theta_M/e < \theta < \theta_M/e) = 2/e \approx 74.04\%$, similarly, $P(-\theta_M/3 < \theta < \theta_M/3) \approx 70.0\%$, in summary , continuous random variables of L function concentrically scatter in area near to its mean value than normal function does.

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